

The Situation of School Violation at Cho Moi High School

Le Ngoc Luat

Bac Kan Education Center for Children with Disabilities

SUMMARY: In about a semester of observation, research with 200 research subjects including male and female students in all three grades 10, 11, 12. Survey results on sexual violence in Cho Moi high school show that sexual violence occurs through many different manifestations. Research shows that there has been school violence here through different forms such as physical violence, emotional violence, sexual violence.

KEYWORDS: school violence; students; school

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the work of preventing and preventing violence in the school environment still faces many difficulties and certain limitations.

One of the basic reasons leading to this situation is that education administrators, staff, and teachers still lack basic knowledge and skills about social work in schools as well as public methods of group consultation work in schools.

School violence is a common problem in schools, occurring in most countries around the world. Many countries around the world are doing research on this issue in order to find radical solutions in reducing the situation of school violence. Since 1950, the United Nations Organization has discussed measures to prevent crime committed by minors (every 5 years). Through studying the topics, the research work can be divided into basic research directions such as:

The author group Nasel and collaborators with the topic "Bullying behavior among American youth: prevalence and relationship with psychosocial adjustment" carried out in 2001. Research results suggest that in the United States, bullying behavior among adolescents is widespread and significant in nature. Issues of bullying are worthy of attention and concern, both for future research and for prevention.

Author Ma Ngoc The (1998) in the research project "The influence of informal friends on children's delinquent behavior". According to research, there is a significant increase in criminal behavior among adolescents. In addition, the study also said that "informal friends play an important role in influencing children's perception and behavior, making them commit crimes from passive to conscious (55%). For ages 17-18, delinquency fell to 17.5% due to better self-perception in this age group than in adolescents" [1].

In the topic "Problematic behavior of adolescents: parental influences", researcher Nguyen Thi Hoa stated that "parental relationship personality has a profound influence on problematic behavior". subject matter of minors. In addition, the author points out that parents' behaviors with their children in today's society mainly follow two trends: parents lack attention, take care of their children or are too indulgent. The author concludes that, among the causes of problematic behavior in children at this age, parents are partly responsible. The problem is that there should be proper care and education from the parents of the children" [2].

Approaching the theory of social control and the theory of social imitation in the study "Factors affecting school violence from the perspective of approaching social theory" of author Phan Thuan (2014). factors affecting school violence, he said that "the earlier the lack of social control and the earlier the opportunity to be exposed to violent behavior, the greater the risk of violent behavior." [3].

2. RESEARCH RESULTS

In about a semester, observing, researching and making statistics from mass organizations, especially from class teachers, at the same time, the author of the thesis selects students who are suitable for the topic, with 200 students. Research subjects include both male and female students in all three grades 10, 11, 12. The proportion of male students is higher than that of female students. Through the questionnaire, the author of the thesis obtained the following specific results:

Table: Actual situation of school violence at Cho Moi high school

Physical violence

Content	Level				Average
	Often times(%)	Sometimes times (%)	Rarely times (%)	Never times (%)	
1. I was quarreled by a group of friends inside or outside of school	0	8 (4.1%)	38 (19.1%)	154 (76.8%)	1.5
2. I was beaten, punched, slapped, kicked, pulled my hair, pushed down, splashed ink on my clothes, ripped my clothes, kicked, scratched,	0	14 (7%)	38 (19.1%)	148 (73.9%)	1.33
3. I was attacked with a ruler, knife, brick, stone...	0	2 (1.2%)	28 (14.1%)	170 (84.7%)	1.31
Average					1.38

Mental violence

Content	Level				Average
	Often times(%)	Sometimes times (%)	Rarely times (%)	Never times (%)	
1. I was labeled with bad, unkind nicknames that make me shy and embarrassed	37 (18.5%)	60 (30.2%)	74 (37%)	29 (14.3%)	2.52
2. My friends say bad things behind my back	48 (24.1%)	57 (28.5%)	72 (36%)	23 (11.4%)	2.65
3. I was despised, ridiculed	21 (10.5%)	40 (20%)	84 (42%)	55 (27.5%)	2.14
4. I was directly provoked, called and texted threateningly	16 (7.8%)	20 (10.2%)	44 (22.1%)	120 (59.9%)	1.66
5. I was spread unkind rumors	24 (12.1%)	41 (20.4%)	74 (37.1%)	61 (30.4%)	2.14
6. I was isolated, isolated from other friends	14 (7.1%)	24 (12%)	58 (29.1%)	104 (51.8%)	1.74
Average					2.14

Sexual violence

Content	Level				Average
	Often times(%)	Sometimes times (%)	Rarely times (%)	Never times (%)	
1. I was commented on, commenting on parts of your body, such as your butt, chest and other sensitive parts	3 (1.3%)	9 (4.5%)	28 (14%)	160 (80.2%)	1.27
2. I was intentionally looked at or touched by you in my sensitive place	8 (4%)	12 (5.9%)	30 (15%)	150 (75.1%)	1.39

3. I was photographed without consent and the sensitive pictures were posted on social media	0	0	0	0	0
4. I was sent pornographic links and publications over the phone	0	8 (4%)	19 (9.4%)	173 (86.5%)	1.18
5. I was forced, forced to have sex	0	0	0	0	0
Average					0.77

Through the data table of the above survey results, it shows that school violence still occurs in many different forms and levels at Cho Moi High School, specifically:

One is physical violence: Through the survey on three manifestations of violence, the author found that: The average score of the form of physical violence is low (1.38), specifically the expression "I have suffered from physical violence . group of friends who quarrel inside or outside of school " has the highest overall average score (1.5), the expression " I was hit, punched, slapped, kicked, pulled my hair, pushed down, splashed ink on my clothes, ripped tearing clothes, touching, scratching, " ranked second with an average score of 1.33; and the expression " I was attacked with a ruler, knife, brick, stone... .. " had the lowest average score (1.31). Also according to the combined results from the survey, it means that the percentage of students who have never experienced physical violence is also very high .

The second is mental violence: The survey shows that, compared with physical violence, mental violence accounts for a much higher rate than physical violence. The mean score for mental violence is 2.14. Expressions of mental violence such as: "I was labeled with bad, unkind nicknames that made me shy and embarrassed", "I was told bad things by friends behind my back", "I was despised. . high.

Specifically as follows: At the level of "Often ", the expression "being said bad things behind your back by friends " accounted for the highest rate (24.1%) . This is also easy to explain when students are influenced by a Vietnamese habit of prying and commenting on others. The expression "assigned with bad and unkind nicknames makes me shy and embarrassed" accounts for a fairly high rate and at a regular level (18.5%). This is also a common expression in schools over the years. It is possible that when assigning students, they are not aware that this will affect the psychology or development of the person being assigned, even though the assignor may not be intentional. In addition, manifestations of psychological violence were also assessed at a regular level, but at a low level. Thus, the survey results show that physical violence has a certain difference with mental violence.

Also in the form of mental violence shows that the rate of "sometimes" occurrence is much higher than that of "Often". This result shows that, compared with physical violence, mental violence occurs more often and is more common at Cho Moi High School. Visually, it is easy to see that physical violence manifests more clearly than mental violence, so mental violence has not been paid as much attention as physical violence, although mental violence occurs. Therefore, through this study, it is possible for the staff of Cho Moi High School to have a more correct awareness of both mental and physical violence.

In general, in the form of mental violence, the expression "I was told bad things by my friends behind my back" had the highest average score, converted into a rating scale, it reached level 3 (quite common) and It is also the most common occurrence of school violence in Cho Moi High School. Other manifestations of mental violence had lower mean scores and conversion scores were all below average.

Third, sexual violence: In our Vietnamese culture, "sexual violence" is one of those issues that are relatively delicate and difficult to measure, especially when it comes to this issue in student age. Therefore, this can be considered as a new point of the thesis. With the current situation of sexual violence, it is extremely necessary and important to frankly recognize, face and analyze content related to sexual violence in the school environment. We know that the age from 15 to 18 years old is the period when children are in the puberty stage, as well as having a clear and strong development of sex, so learning about gender and sexuality knowledge is very important. It is necessary and correct to be able to help them have the right view of this issue, thereby knowing how to protect themselves, their friends and the people around them. Therefore, instead of avoiding mentioning gender and sexuality issues, we should be open and methodical in conveying and orienting children with necessary and sufficient content.

The analysis of the survey results on the situation of sexual violence in Cho Moi High School shows that sexual violence

occurs through many different manifestations. Specifically: 1.3% of students said that they were "commented and commented on body parts, such as buttocks, bust and other sensitive parts". at the level of "Often", 4.5% said this expression was "sometimes" and 14% "rarely". In the expression " I was intentionally looked at or touched by you in my sensitive place ", 4% of students rated it "Often", 5.9% rated it "sometimes" and 15 % replies are rare. The expression " I was sent pornographic links and publications by phone " had 4% of students think that it was "sometimes", 9.4% was "rarely".

3. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and assessment of the current situation of school violence, I would like to make the following recommendations:

For schools: Continue to build a safe and friendly school environment; Creating conditions for group consultation activities of students at risk of school violence to be effectively organized and implemented; Building a School Counseling Center.

For school psychology counselors: Regularly cultivate necessary knowledge and skills on social work to improve capacity and skills when working with target groups; Find out, firmly grasp the characteristics of the situation and needs of victims of school violence, thereby developing appropriate support activities; Diversify support activities, actively connect resources in the process of assisting students with violent behavior

For students' families: Regularly connecting and coordinating with the school, parents increase their interest in their children and improve their own understanding of school social work as well as parenting skills. .

For students who commit violent acts: equip themselves with necessary knowledge and skills; learn more legal knowledge to know the consequences caused by them; actively explore and seek out support activities at school.

REFERENCES

1. Ma Ngoc The (1998), *Informal peer group influence on children's delinquent behavior* ; Education Publishing House
2. Nguyen Thi Hoa,(2019) *Problematic behavior of adolescents: parental influences* ", Academy of Social Sciences
3. Phan Thuan (2014), " *Factors affecting school violence from the perspective of approaching social theory* ", scientific report.
4. Brehm , SS (1989), *Social Psychology*, Boston, Houghton Millin Compay
5. Chambers HE (2001), *Effective communication skills* , Cambridge, MA: Perseus.
6. Carl Sommer (2009), *Teen Success In Career & Life Skills* , Advance Publishing, USA.
7. Derek Chechak (2008), *The roles of a social worker* , School of Social Work, King 's University College, UWO .